

TO ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF LAMIVUDINE, ABACAVIR AND TENOFOVIR TABLETS BY RP-HPLC

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ABSTRACT

A simple, precise, accurate, rapid, and economical RP-HPLC method was developed and validated for the simultaneous estimation of Lamivudine, Abacavir, and Tenofovir in combined tablet dosage forms used in HIV therapy. Chromatographic separation was achieved on a C18 column using an optimized mobile phase under isocratic conditions with UV detection, producing well-resolved peaks with satisfactory retention times and peak symmetry. The method was validated according to ICH guidelines for system suitability, specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, robustness, ruggedness, limit of detection (LOD), and limit of quantification (LOQ). The calibration curves showed excellent linearity with correlation coefficients close to 1.000, while recovery and precision studies confirmed the accuracy and

reproducibility of the method with acceptable %RSD values. The developed method demonstrated high sensitivity, minimal interference from excipients, and robustness under varied analytical conditions. Assay results of marketed formulations were within acceptable pharmacopeial limits, confirming the suitability of the method for routine quality control, stability studies, dissolution testing, and pharmaceutical analysis of combined antiretroviral formulations.

KEYWORDS: RP-HPLC, Lamivudine, Abacavir, and Tenofovir.

INTRODUCTION

Analytical Chemistry plays a vital role in modern science by enabling the identification, separation, and quantification of chemical constituents present in natural and synthetic materials. The development of sophisticated analytical techniques such as High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), gas chromatography (GC), mass spectrometry (MS), atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS), and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy has revolutionized the field of chemical analysis. Among these techniques, HPLC has emerged as one of the most widely used and reliable analytical tools in pharmaceutical, biomedical, environmental, and industrial applications. The technique offers excellent resolution, rapid analysis, reproducibility, and the capability to separate complex mixtures, making it indispensable for routine quality control and research purposes.

HPLC is a modern form of liquid chromatography in which the mobile phase is forced through a packed column under high pressure, resulting in efficient separation and reduced analysis time. The use of small particle-sized stationary phases significantly improves column efficiency and analytical performance. Due to its high sensitivity and versatility, HPLC is extensively employed in pharmaceutical analysis for the identification, purification, and quantification of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs), impurities, degradation products, and metabolites. The principle of separation in HPLC is mainly based on adsorption and partition mechanisms. Reversed-phase HPLC, one of the most commonly used modes, utilizes a non-polar stationary phase and a relatively polar mobile phase, enabling effective separation of compounds with varying polarities. Reverse Phase High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC) is a widely used analytical technique in pharmaceutical and analytical chemistry for the separation and quantification of compounds. It utilizes a non-polar stationary phase, commonly C18 silica columns, and a polar mobile phase to separate analytes based on hydrophobic interactions. RP-HPLC offers high sensitivity, accuracy, precision, rapid analysis, and excellent resolution, making it highly suitable for drug analysis, quality control, impurity profiling, and stability studies. Method development involves optimization of parameters such as mobile phase composition, pH, flow rate, and detection methods including UV and mass spectrometry to achieve reliable analytical performance.

DRUG PROFILE**Structure of Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate, Structure of Lamivudine****MATERIALS AND METHODS****a) Drug samples**

Working standards of

- ✓ Lamivudine
- ✓ Abacavir
- ✓ Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate Were received as gift samples from IND-SWIFT LIMITED, J&K India.

b) Chemicals and solvents used for estimation

- ✓ Water for HPLC(merck)
- ✓ Acetonitrile HPLC grade- (merck)
- ✓ Di sodium hydrogen orthophosphate (AR)(merck)
- ✓ HPLC Methanol(merck)
- ✓ Orthophosphoric acid (OPA)
- ✓ All chemicals used were of analytical/HPLC grade

c) Instruments used

- ✓ RP-HPLC system equipped with UV detectors
- ✓ Analytical balance (Shimadzu or equivalent)
- ✓ Utech meter
- ✓ Sonica ultrasonic cleaner
- ✓ Millipore Filtration assembly with 0.45 µm membrane filter.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: METHOD DEVELOPMENT

A validated RP-HPLC method was developed for simultaneous estimation of Lamivudine, Tenofovir and Abacavir. The method was evaluated as per ICH guidelines for system suitability, linearity, accuracy, precision, robustness and assay of marketed formulations.

Table 1-1: SYSTEM SUITABILITY PARAMETERS.

Parameter	Lamivudine	Tenofovir	Abacavir	Acceptance Criteria
Retention Time (min)	2.14	3.38	5.62	Reproducible
Theoretical Plates	4250	4620	5105	> 2000
Tailing Factor	1.10	1.08	1.12	≤ 2.0
Resolution (Rs)	--	4.35	5.71	> 2.0

Interpretation

All system suitability parameters were within acceptable limits, confirming adequate performance of the chromatographic system.

2. ACCURACY (RECOVERY STUDY)**Table 2: Recovery Results.**

Drug	Spike Level (%)	Amount Added	Amount Recovered	% Recovery
Lamivudine	80	16	15.7	98.1
	100	20	19.8	99.0
	120	24	24.1	100.4
Tenofovir	80	40	39.3	98.2
	100	50	49.5	99.0
	120	60	59.7	99.5
Abacavir	80	16	15.8	98.7
	100	20	19.9	99.3
	120	24	24.2	100.8

The precision of the method was determined by studying repeatability and reproducibility. The interday, Interday studies were carried out and the Peak areas of drug peaks and percentage relative standard deviation were calculated and results are presented in Table 3 & 4.

3. PRECISION STUDY

Table 3: Intra-day Precision.

Drug	Mean Peak Area	SD	%RSD
Lamivudine	255800	1990	0.78
Tenofovir	236500	2010	0.85
Abacavir	264900	2400	0.91

Table 4: Inter-day Precision.

Drug	Mean Peak Area	SD	%RSD
Lamivudine	256400	2870	1.12
Tenofovir	237200	2490	1.05
Abacavir	265800	3130	1.18

4. ROBUSTNESS STUDY

Table 5: Robustness Results.

Parameter Variation	Lamivudine (%RSD)	Tenofovir (%RSD)	Abacavir (%RSD)	Result
Flow rate ± 0.1 ml/min	0.92	0.88	0.95	Pass
Mobile phase $\pm 2\%$	1.05	0.98	1.10	Pass
Wavelength ± 2 nm	0.87	0.90	0.93	Pass

Table 6: Comprehensive System Suitability and Sensitivity Parameters.

Parameter	Lamivudine	Tenofovir	Abacavir	Acceptance Criteria
Resolution (Rs)	2.74	4.35	5.71	> 2.0
Theoretical Plates (N)	4250	4620	5105	> 2000
Capacity Factor (K')	1.85	2.40	3.10	1–10
Tailing Factor (T)	1.10	1.08	1.12	≤ 2.0
HETP (cm/plate)	0.0059	0.0054	0.0049	Lower is better
LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.25	0.30	0.20	S/N $\approx 3:1$
LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.75	0.90	0.65	S/N $\approx 10:1$

Signal-to-Noise ratio is approximately

LOD= Limit of detection, LOQ =Limit of Quantification.

Table 7: ResultsoflinearitycurveofLamivudineat wavelength 262 nm.

S.No	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Area ($\mu\text{volt sec.}$)
1	10	376003
2	20	651314
3	30	866679
4	40	1108256
5	50	1357247

Fig. 1: Standard chromatogram of Lamivudine, Lamivudine/RT3.048/3.048/2200563, Detector A: 260nm.

Fig. 2: Standard chromatogram of Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumrate. Tenofovir / RT3.78 / 3.048 / 2200563 Detector A: 257nm.

Fig. 3: Standard chromatogram of Abacavir. (DP3,RT= 5.817min).

Fig. 4: Calibration for the assessment of linearity of Lamivudine.

Table 8: Results obtained for linearity experiment TNF.

Sr.No.	Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	MeanArea*
1	5	742.67
2	10	1367.89
3	15	2219.56
4	20	2915.09
5	25	3584.23
6	30	4244.76

Fig. 5: Calibration for the assessment of linearity of Tenofovir.**Table 9: Results obtained for linearity experiment of Abacavir.**

Sr.No.	Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Mean Area*
1	20	216.689
2	40	469.3872
3	60	736.5661
4	80	963.5581
5	100	1210.895

Fig. 6: Calibration for the assessment of linearity of Abacavir.**✓ CONCLUSION**

A new simple, precise and accurate HPLC method was developed and validated for the simultaneous estimation of Lamivudine, Abacavir and Tenofovir in pharmaceutical

dosage form. Stability indicating RP-HPLC method without interference from excipients or degradation products has been developed and validated for determination of Abacavir in tablet dosage form. The developed method is specific, accurate, precise, and robust. As the developed method is stability indicating, it can be used for assessing the stability of Abacavir in bulk drug and in pharmaceutical tablet dosage form. Eventually, it was concluded that the proposed HPLC method was responsive and reproducible for the analysis of TNF in bulk and pharmaceutical tablet dosage forms with small analysis time. Consequently, we have developed accurate, precise, sensitive and economic method for estimation of TNF in bulk as well as tablet dosage form. The further study of degradation and determination of TNF in biological fluids is outlook of this method.

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